

imec

MULTI SENSOR AI FOR SURFACE FAULT DETECTION

DR. ING. ALI ANWAR

WHO AM I?

- Principal Investigator @ Adapt-I program, imec – IDLab – University of Antwerp
- Leading a team of 5 researchers
- Research Interests include
 - Domain Generalization in Deep Learning
 - Robust Reinforcement Learning
 - Data-efficient Learning

IDLAB OVERVIEW

PART OF IMEC + EMBEDDED IN UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP & GHENT UNIVERSITY

IDLab Antwerp

120+ Members

- 8 Professors
- 10+ Post-Docs
- 80+ Researchers
- 4 Support Staff
- 5 Business Developers

IDLab Research Activities

- Foundational & Applied Research
- Developing technology for Connected Systems, AI and IoT
- 500+ Collaborations with innovative industry

OUTLINE

- Introduction to HAIROAD Project
- Opportunistic Sensing
- Strengths and Weaknesses of Multiple Sensors
- HAIROAD Dataset
- AI Models
- Results and Learning Outcomes

OVERALL BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Mobility and road infrastructure maintenance cost

30 % of municipalities' investments goes to the maintenance of mobility and road infrastructure

Current manual inspection is nonoptimal

Labour intensive
Subjective evaluation
Possible out of date view
Oversimplified forecast models

Scientifically sound methodology

A modern condition monitoring and pavement management system is highly needed in this sector

OVERVIEW & RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Overview HAIRoad:

INSPECTION AUTOMATION VIA OPPORTUNISTIC SENSING

- **Current status:**
 - Humans are involved in visual inspection
 - Manual inspection takes place on a daily basis
 - Error Prone due to repetitive nature of the task
- **Ideal future status: “opportunistic” sensing**
 - Automation in data acquisition during routine operations
 - No dedicated human required to process and acquire the images
 - AI detects the faults on the images in real-time and regular basis

From

To

DEVELOPMENT OF THE SENSOR SETUP

- Multi-modal sensor setup for the road surface fault detection in all weather conditions

3D Sonar

LiDAR

Camera

SENSOR SETUP ON THE VEHICLE

- Easily mountable
- Edge compute, communication and power systems available onboard

WHY DO WE NEED SO MANY SENSORS? - I

We operate in multiple scenarios such as Fog, Mist, Rain, different types of surfaces

WHY DO WE NEED SO MANY SENSORS? – II

- We measure different types of faults
 - Different texture
 - Geometry
 - Depth

STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF HAIRROAD SENSORS

Sensor	Fault Type	Operating Conditions
Camera	Detects texture, geometry, and objects that can be seen visually	Good lighting conditions, doesn't work in low light or misty/foggy conditions
LiDAR	Detects depth and 3D geometry well (e.g., cracks, rutting, subsidence)	Performs well in different lighting conditions, but doesn't work in misty, rainy conditions
Sonar	Detects depth and 3D geometry such as potholes, humps and rutting	Performs well in low light, misty, rainy, foggy conditions, but resolution low
Sound Vibration	Detects surface degradation, stone loss, crack and pothole density	Difficult to classify the types of faults compared to visual sensing

THE BEST SOLUTION IS TO COMBINE THEM

HAIROAD DATASET

COURTESY OF ATAM

Annotated dataset in Belgium:

- 3677 images for asphalt; 1217 images for concrete; 124 images for element

Classes covered

- Longitudinal Crack
- Transversal Crack
- Alligator Crack
- Rutting
- Missing Material
- Fraying

HAIROAD LABELLING TOOL OPEN SOURCED

COURTESY OF INVILAB, UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP

Source code: https://github.com/InViLabUAntwerp/Hairoad_PointCloud_labels/

GLOBAL ARCHITECTURE (UPDATE INCLUDE MLOPS)

PAVEMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

COURTESY OF INUITS, ASASENSE

Devices/ Heatmap

Search by address Remove ⌵ ⌶

Legend

- Filter by date
- Filter by device state ID
- Filter by device ID

Loading map data...

Logout

PAVEsense regions / Port Of Antwerp Last results: 2025-06 Data version

Table Map Export

ID	STREET NAME	SURFACE TYPE	REFERENCE SPEED	Macro1	Macro2	Mega1	Mega2	Waviness	eIRI	Authority
249	Bosstraat_LAN	asphalt	41 km/h	0.62	0.77	0.44	0.32	0.45	8.4 m/km	
267	Scheldelaan / N101	asphalt, concrete	57 km/h	0.92	0.91	0.29	0.01	0.02	4.7 m/km	
268	Ordamstraat	asphalt	42 km/h	0.35	0.32	0.23	0.35	0.33	3.9 m/km	
269	Muisbroeklaan	asphalt	35 km/h	0.77	0.53	0.12	0.09	0.14	6.8 m/km	
270		asphalt	41 km/h	0.78	0.69	0.04	0.03	0.04	8.6 m/km	
348	A12	asphalt	41 km/h	0.88	0.82	0.21	0.07	0.1	4.1 m/km	
349	A12	asphalt	35 km/h	0.47	0.36	0.07	0.17	0.09	8.4 m/km	
449	Antwerpsebaan	asphalt	71 km/h	0.16	0.15	0.74	0.92	0.87	1.6 m/km	
755	Leugenberg	asphalt	50 km/h	0.55	0.43	0.21	0.16	0.13	3.7 m/km	Good Stad Antwerpen
756	Kruisschansweg	concrete	30 km/h	0.95	0.76	0.08	0.03	0.02	5.9 m/km	Good Agentschap Wegen en Verkeer - District Antwerpen

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AI MODELS

- Camera only
- Sonar only
- Camera – LiDAR fusion

CAMERA MODEL

RESULTS

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Asphalt - Longitudinal crack	0.67	0.58	0.62	252
Asphalt - Transversal crack	0.85	0.89	0.87	532
Asphalt - Alligator crack	0.76	0.78	0.77	345
Asphalt - Missing material	0.75	0.54	0.63	235
Asphalt - Fraying	0.67	0.47	0.55	194
Asphalt - Sweating	0.50	0.86	0.63	7
Concrete - Longitudinal crack	0.62	0.56	0.59	9
Concrete - Transversal crack	0.83	0.88	0.86	191
Concrete - Corner crack	0.57	0.44	0.50	18
Concrete - Alligator crack	0.60	0.33	0.43	9
Concrete - Missing material	0.72	0.52	0.60	106
Concrete - Open longitudinal joint	0.69	0.56	0.62	102
Concrete - Open transversal joint	0.64	0.76	0.70	74
Element - Broken stones	0.71	0.42	0.53	12
Element - Loose stones	1.00	0.83	0.91	24
Element - Missing stones	0.00	0.00	0.00	3
micro avg	0.76	0.70	0.73	2113
macro avg	0.48	0.43	0.45	2113
weighted avg	0.76	0.70	0.72	2113
samples avg	0.74	0.74	0.72	2113

SONAR MODEL

SONAR RESULTS

- Good performance on classes such as
 - Broken Stones, Corner Crack, Fraying and Subsidence
- Struggling on classes such as
 - Alligator crack, Transversal Crack, Missing Material

CAMERA-LIDAR FUSION MODEL

CAMERA-LIDAR FUSION MODEL - RESULTS

CONCLUSIONS

- HAIROAD proposes a multi-sensor AI based automation solution for the problem of road surface monitoring
- The solution is inexpensive < 10K in hardware costs
- The research has resulted in multiple AI models and a dataset containing multiple BRRC classes for the Belgian roads

QUESTIONS?

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